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Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

Technical Memorandum To Support Task 3.3
[Guidelines For Fractography]

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

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1 Introduction

The aim of the FRACTESUS project is to join European and International efforts to establish the foundation of small specimen fracture toughness validation and demonstration such that Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) Regulators have confidence in accepting the results of tests on small specimens within NPP safety cases and justifications. The reference specimen geometry is the miniature Compact Tension specimen, 10 mm x 10 mm x 4 mm, ($\sim 0.16T$ C(T) or $1/6T$ C(T)). This geometry is of particular interest to the nuclear industry as historic surveillance capsules include Charpy impact specimens, and up to eight $0.16T$ C(T) specimens can be manufactured from a single broken Charpy specimen (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 Four $0.16T$ C(T) specimens as extracted from a broken half Charpy impact specimen.

An important step towards Regulatory acceptance of data derived from small specimens is the demonstration that the process of fracture is equivalent in small and large specimens. Metallographic investigation of the fracture surface (fractography) is an important contributor to this demonstration. Within FRACTESUS, the objectives of Work Package 3 (Fracture mechanics testing and post-test analysis) include the exploration of the fractographic peculiarities of tested $0.16T$ C(T) specimens. This will be achieved by a combination of quantitative fractography of the entire fracture surface and the location of fracture initiation sites.

This Technical Memorandum (in support of Milestone MS9) outlines guidance for members of the consortium planning to perform fractography. It is based on practice at the UK's National Nuclear Laboratory and is set out as guidance for colleagues with limited experience in fractography. It therefore contains background information to justify the recommendations of particular practices. It is intended

to be the first step in obtaining feedback from consortium members in defining best practice and assisting colleagues to perform consistent and informative fractography.

2 Guidelines For Fractography

2.1 Sample Provision

The first step in performing fractography is the provision of a good quality fracture surface. Care should be taken at all times to avoid touching or knocking the surface. Prior to testing, the sample should be marked in such a way that each broken half will be identifiable without further procedures. Both halves should be retained for fractography.

Avoiding oxidation of a low alloy steel fracture surface becomes more difficult, the further the test temperature is from room temperature. Measures can be taken to reduce condensation on low temperature surfaces or gaseous oxidation of high temperature surfaces, including testing in a dry atmosphere or transferring the fractured specimen halves to a dry or non-oxidising environment. One such example is the immediate transfer of a broken sample to a beaker of alcohol as it warms to room temperature.

The preservation of specimens for short times prior to fractography is best achieved by storage in a desiccator. Each half-specimen should be wrapped separately in lint-free material prior to storage. If storage in a desiccator is not convenient then the wrapped specimens should at least be stored in the presence of a desiccant. (Most desiccants have a limited utility and the manufacturer's guidelines should be followed concerning regular renewal or replacement. Many desiccants can be renewed by a short period of heating to drive off the water absorbed during service.)

Prior to analysis, the sample should be cleaned of oils, dust and fibres which may obscure the fracture surface or charge in the scanning electron microscope (SEM). This is conveniently performed by placing the sample in a beaker of alcohol or acetone in an ultrasonic bath to loosen the dirt, removing the specimen and rinsing the surface with a squirt of solvent. If the appearance of the ultrasonic bath suggests that the original surface was contaminated, this step should be repeated with fresh solvent. If there is a concern that residues may be left on the surface by evaporating solvent, then rinsing should be continued until the solvent runs off the end of the sample. In preparation for initiation site fractography, it is best to tilt the sample so that the flow of rinsing solvent is from the notch root towards the back of the sample as this keeps residues away from the region of greatest interest. Similarly drying in a stream of air is less likely to leave residues than drying in still air.

2.2 Sample Selection

It is valuable to inspect the fracture surfaces of all the samples tested to gain a general sense of the fracture behaviour e.g. whether the samples appear to have failed in a similar manner, which samples are cleanest or least damaged. It is not, however, common for all types of fractography to be performed on all samples in a campaign. Samples may be selected to show fracture behaviour at different

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temperatures / levels of toughness for a given material, or to compare behaviour in different materials at a given temperature or level of toughness. In a round robin, such as FRACTESUS, the choice should be discussed beforehand to ensure consistency and allow meaningful comparisons to be made.

Within FRACTESUS, and for small specimen testing in general, the range of test temperatures is likely to be small, so selection on the basis of toughness level may offer the most meaningful comparisons.

It is generally agreed that brittle fracture in low alloy steels is a weakest link process near the lower shelf [1]. A single or dominant initiation site is produced in the lower transition region. On the lower shelf itself, however, multiple sites are more frequently observed. When performing initiation site fractography it is, therefore, best to select a sample which failed in the lower transition rather than on the lower shelf. As the test temperature increases, the proportion of ductile failure increases. Where patches of ductility have formed, the brittle crack front will be deflected. The brittle crack path will deviate around the patches and may, locally, turn back on itself as previously-occluded ligaments break. This makes tracing the brittle crack path and identifying the initiation site more difficult. The optimum sample is thus one that fractures at a sufficiently high temperature that a single initiation site dominates, but at a sufficiently low temperature that the crack path is mostly radial from the initiation site. A specimen which failed at a toughness level between 20 and 30 MPa \sqrt{m} is usually optimal. Specimens which have failed at higher toughness levels can still be analysed successfully, but the brittle crack path will become more convoluted and progressively more difficult to trace as the toughness increases. Within the FRACTESUS project, the testing protocol is likely to produce failures in range 50-100 MPa \sqrt{m} rather than in the optimal toughness range. It will make the location of initiation sites within FRACTESUS easier to identify if the lowest-toughness samples available are selected.

2.3 Quantitative Fractography

This Section and Section 2.4 consider the reasons for performing quantitative and initiation site fractography within FRACTESUS, and outline procedures for obtaining useful information. The precise conditions under which the scanning electron microscope (SEM) should be operated in order to acquire images will vary from microscope to microscope. It is, however, useful to appreciate the factors which experienced fractographers have optimized in their investigations. The fractographic procedures recommended at HZDR are, therefore, detailed in Section 2.5.

2.3.1 Assessment of Fatigue Crack Front

The shape of the fatigue crack front should be measured for all samples according to ASTM E1921-21, section 8.8.1 or equivalent, to show whether the toughness measurement is valid.

Further quantitative fractography will be performed on a sub-set of samples, as agreed by the consortium.

2.3.2 Measurement of Preliminary Ductile Crack Extension

Ductile crack extensions prior to brittle fracture initiation are expected to be small and intermittent for samples failing with toughnesses less than $100 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. Most valid tests on 0.16 C(T) samples will fall into this category. Nonetheless it contributes to the aims of the FRACTESUS project to demonstrate that the samples are failing in a conventional manner, including the magnitude of preliminary ductile crack extension.

Measurement of any initial ductile microcrack extension requires scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Measurements should be performed on both fracture faces where possible.

Divide the thickness of the specimen into 10 equal sections; this defines 9 internal boundaries crossing the microcrack region, as shown in *Figure 2a*. Measure the ductile region at those locations and take the average.

Suitable magnifications at which these measurements should be taken are in the range $\times 250 - \times 500$.

Figure 2. Suitable measurement locations for determining (a) width of preliminary ductile crack extension (b) edge effects. (SAW PS SOL)

2.3.3 Measurement of Slant Fracture

The aim of the fracture toughness test is to determine the plane strain fracture toughness. The sides of a test specimen are not in plane strain and fail in a more ductile mode than the main part. The specimen size criteria for valid toughness testing are designed to ensure that the failure process is dominated by plane strain and small scale yielding. The dominance of plane strain and small scale yielding can be demonstrated by showing that the proportion of the specimen exhibiting slant fracture (enhanced ductility, shearing off) is small.

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Divide the width of the fracture surface into two. At five, evenly-spaced locations in the half closer to the precrack front (see *Figure 2b*), measure the width of the slant region (where present) on each edge of the sample.

Only one fracture face need be measured. Suitable magnifications for these measurements are in the range x250 – x500.

2.3.4 Characterisation of Main Fracture Surface

The aim of quantitative fractography is to assess the proportion of the fracture surface which has failed by different fracture modes e.g. transgranular, intergranular, microvoid coalescence, shearing off, cleavage, quasi-cleavage, while minimizing operator bias. The first step involves identifying “the fracture surface”. For the 0.16 C(T) specimens in this study, it excludes the precrack, the stretch zone, any initial ductile microcrack extension and the regions of shearing off or slant fracture at the edges or back face of the *sample*. *Any portion covering more than half the area shaded in Figure 3 would be suitable.*

Figure 3. Identification of portion of fracture surface suitable for quantification.

To make a statistically significant assessment of the different fracture modes, it is necessary to measure at least 200 points. This is straightforward with an automated SEM stage: Define the area to be investigated, set up a grid 10x20 or 15x15 to cover the entire area, then move the stage automatically from position to position on the grid. When assessing the fracture mode at a given location it is important not to be distracted by the majority feature or a particularly interesting feature in the field of view. One way to avoid this is to set up cross-hairs over the image to define the central point. At each location in the grid, identify only the fracture mode at the precise position of the cross-hairs, even if it is a piece of dirt. For predominantly brittle fracture, most modes will be identifiable at a magnification of

x2000. In some cases, it may be helpful to increase and decrease the magnification to aid identification. In these cases, using the cross-hairs helps to ensure that the same point is being considered at each magnification, regardless of the relative ease with which neighbouring features can be identified.

An example of different categories assigned to features found at the cross-hair location in a low alloy steel is shown in *Figure 4*. The categories used for the fracture surface in *Figure 4* were described as:

1. Cleavage
2. Ductile microvoid coalescence
3. Featureless/smooth surface
4. Particle
5. Secondary Crack
6. Oxide/dirt

In most investigations, it is necessary to include additional categories, such as

7. Intergranular
8. Damaged
9. Not identified

In this particular investigation, category 3 (featureless) was mainly allocated to regions which were so small that their nature was unclear, as found within the two regions ringed beside the “3” in *Figure 4*. These small features could have been transgranular cleavage facets too small to have developed distinct chevron marks / river lines; very small, isolated intergranular facets or small regions of ductility (shearing off). A large, flat region without features such as river lines or chevron markings is more likely to be identifiable as intergranular or damaged

Figure 4 Examples of features on a low alloy steel fracture surface.

If numbers of ambiguous or unidentified points become significant, then operator experience and data presentation become important. Operator bias can be checked by repeating the analysis with a second operator. For a material similar to that shown in *Figure 4*, two operators assigned categories as shown in *Figure 5*. The more experienced fractographer was confident in assigning as “ductile” more of the regions that the less experienced operator left as “smooth”. In consequence, the fraction of the surface described as “cleavage” was changed only by a few % (as expected when different grids were used), but the ratio of cleavage / ductile changed significantly. When compiling work from several sources, it is, thus, best to represent the data directly, rather than as (or at least in addition to) ratios.

Figure 5 Repeat assessments of a given sample.

2.3.5 Numbers of Samples

It is recommended that the shape of the precrack front (Section 2.3.1), the extent of ductile precracking (Section 2.3.2) and the amount of slant fracture (Section 2.3.3) be measured as part of the overview of each sample fractured within FRACTESUS. Quantitative fractography (Section 2.3.4) should be performed on at least one sample from each material tested by a partner. If possible, this should be a sample from which the toughness data will not be censored in a Master curve analysis.

2.4 Initiation Site Fractography

Initiation site fractography will be performed on a subset of samples within FRACTESUS to provide additional insight into the conditions under which fracture in small specimens replicate fracture in large specimens. Demonstrating that the fracture initiation site is located well within the region experiencing plane strain and small scale yielding would support the use of 0.16 C(T) specimens. More generally, determining whether the initiation site remains within the plane strain region as the validity limit is approached (or exceeded) may cast light on the use of $M=30$ in the definition of the limiting K_{Jc} value in ASTM Standard E1921-20 [2]:

$$K_{Jc} \leq \sqrt{\left(\frac{Eb_0\sigma_{YS}}{M(1-\nu^2)}\right)} \quad \text{or} \quad b > \frac{MJ_c}{\sigma_{YS}}; \quad M = 30$$

Identifying the fracture initiating features provides information to compare with initiators in larger specimens, demonstrating whether there is any bias in the availability of types of initiators with specimen size.

The initiation site of a monotonic fracture surface can be identified when the main fracture mode is transgranular cleavage. Even when this is the case, the influence of the underlying microstructure, the distribution of other fracture modes and the degree of preservation of the surface can make the site

difficult to locate. In addition, more than one type of initiator may be present in a given material. In consequence, it is recommended that multiple samples from a given material be used for initiation site fractography, to ensure that a complete picture of the process can be gained. Within FRACTESUS, it is recommended that at least five samples be investigated per material selected.

If the specimen is not active and may be handled, it is helpful to perform an initial, visual inspection of the fracture surface. Tilting the sample back and forth affects the way in which light reflects from facets and can highlight the way in which the surface fans out from a particular point, giving a preliminary indication of the approximate position of the fracture initiation site. Where the steel microstructure has coarse features, such as weld beads, stringers or segregated zones, these may also become evident. Knowledge of the locations of these structures aids in the interpretation of magnified images.

The two halves of the broken specimen should be mounted and analysed together where possible. This increases the amount of information available as features occluded on one face may be readily evident on the other. It also allows the location of the initiation site to be confirmed by analysis of the second face. In addition, where the initiation site is a fractured particle, it is often found that only a small part of the particle is left on one face and rendering its composition difficult to determine, while EDX (energy-dispersive x-ray) spectra are readily acquired from the larger portion on the other face.

When the specimen is mounted in the SEM, it is best examined in secondary electron (SE) mode. The first images should be acquired at as low a magnification as possible so that the entire fracture surface can be recorded. This will require a long working distance. Classic descriptions of brittle fracture refer to chevron markings and sometimes, the changes in height on the fracture surface are, indeed, strongly marked and fan out symmetrically from a central location in a chevron shape. Generally, the markings that are visible at low magnification in the SEM, are not very strong, and become weaker as the initiation site is approached, as illustrated in *Figure 6*. In *Figure 6*, there appears to be a single initiation site, located close to the tip of the precrack and in the centre of the specimen, in the region indicated by the ring. In *Figure 7*, however, the chevron markings, while clear, point to a location to the right of centre.

Figure 6 Matched pair of fracture surfaces. Chevron markings showing the initiation site to be central (ringed on right-hand image). (Euro A WV11)

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Figure 7 Sample in which around two thirds of the fracture surface emanates from an initiation site to the right of centre, while the remainder is associated with three secondary initiation sites (A, B and C).

It is unwise to use the centre of the general region of the initiation site, as identified at low magnification, as the location of the initiation site as the site itself may be offset from the centre. This is more often the case when the underlying microstructure is varied (as in a weld) or the presence of microvoid coalescence causes the local crack direction to vary. Once the general region of the (main) initiation site has been identified at low magnification, this must be investigated in detail at higher magnification. Better quality imaging will often be achieved at higher magnification with a shorter working distance. The advantage of reducing the working distance depends on the SEM used.

Two types of feature are observed on cleavage facets, chevron markings and river lines, as illustrated in Figure 8. Both are formed from ridges where the facet surface changes height. Chevron markings are the most common, and fan out from the point at which fracture initiated on the facet. Each step in the surface is maintained and becomes higher and more distinct as the crack front proceeds. Chevron markings can be thought of as arrow-heads pointing back to the initiation site. River markings are so called because their appearance is similar to that of a river developing a delta. In this case, several steps form where the crack front crosses from one grain to the next, but these run together as the crack front proceeds. With river markings, the “downstream” direction points towards the initiation site.

Figure 8 Fracture facets close to an initiation site illustrating chevron markings (e.g. in area outlined by blue trapezoid) and river lines (outlined in red). (Euro A WV4)

Both types of facet marking can be followed from facet to facet back to the overall initiation site, as illustrated in Figure 9. The directions of the coloured arrows in Figure 9 show the direction of the analysis, tracing back to the initiation site i.e. opposite to the crack growth direction.

There is no recommended magnification for this procedure. The optimum magnification is one at which the markings on individual facets are visible, but several facets can be observed at once to aid in tracing the overall crack path.

It is good practice to start traces from several different locations in the general area of the initiation site to confirm the significance of the initiation site first observed. This is particularly helpful when patches and skeins of ductility have deflected the crack path, as is likely to be the case for the moderately tough samples that will be available in FRACTESUS. Figure 9 illustrates the confirmation of the initiation site by traces from several parts of the sample, with the path marked by the gold arrows being the most tortuous.

Figure 9 Overview showing the process of tracing back to the fracture initiation site from several different areas (different coloured lines). Initiation site indicated by the red circle.

Once the initiation site has been located on one fracture surface and confirmed with a similar investigation of the matching surface, an illustrative image should be acquired showing converging markings from the immediately surrounding facets. Suitable magnifications are around $\times 5000$. Micrographs should then be acquired at decreasing magnification, so that the identity of the initiation site can be kept evident down to the magnifications at which its location with respect to the precrack front and sample edge can be measured.

High magnifications ($\times 10,000$) are necessary when the nature of the fracture initiator is required. The process is clear when the initiator is an inclusion, and an EDX spectrum can be obtained from the inclusion, as illustrated in Figure 10. Note that the spot size required to obtain a spectrum in a short time, and the accelerating voltage required to excite the characteristic x-rays of interest, mean that even spot measurements taken from inclusions such as that in Figure 10 will contain a significant contribution from the matrix.

Figure 10 (a and b) Images identifying the same initiation site viewed on matching fracture faces (c) High magnification of initiating inclusion showing locations from which spectra were acquired (d) EDX spectrum.

If the initiator is a small Fe-based carbide or a precipitate which has broken flush with the main fracture surface, the initiator can be difficult to identify. Changing the imaging mode to back-scattered electron imaging, and taking EDX maps from the location on the facet from which the facet markings emanate can be helpful, but it is rarely possible to identify the nature of all the initiators in a campaign investigating clean base metals.

2.5 Operational Procedures for Fractography on 0.16C(T) Samples Recommended by HZDR

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) used in fractography: Zeiss EVO 50 with tungsten filament Samples: both halves of the tested 0.16C(T), mounted together

Sample preparation, mounting and sample choice:

- Ultrasonic cleaning (two runs 2 min each, using high purity alcohol)
- Cu sticky-band for contact with holder
- Both sample halves mounted
- Present example: JRQ 0.16C(T) sample
- **“All tested samples”**
 - > 2.5.1 (only overview imaging)
- **“Selected samples”**: at least 5 samples from a series, preferably those with lower K_{Jc} . Additional samples should be analysed, if the results are inconsistent.
 - > 2.5.1 (Overview imaging)
 - > 2.5.2 (Basic characterization of the crack tip and fracture surface)
 - > 2.5.3 (Details of initiation site)
 - > Only in samples where cleavage fracture dominates the sample surface
 - > 2.5.4 (Details of initiation site, high magnification imaging)
 - > Only if an initiation location can be identified or is suspected
 - > 2.5.5 (EDX characterisation)
 - > Only if an initiation location can be identified or is suspected

2.5.1 Overview imaging (all tested samples):

Conditions for overview imaging are:

- 50 μm aperture
- Acceleration voltage = 15 kV
- Imaging mode: depth mode
- Probe current $I_p = 1000 \text{ pA}$
- Image resolution: 3072×2304
- Detector: secondary electrons (SE)
- Press Shift + F2 (to remove lens hysteresis) after every change in working distance or after a significant change in focus, important for correct magnification
- Working distance for imaging: $WD \approx 23 \text{ mm}$; $z = 0.5 \text{ mm}$ (left + right sample fit well in one image)
- Scan parameters: scan speed ≥ 6 ; Line average with $N = 6$; at least 2 min / image
- 2 overview images with both samples
- 1 image of each sample half @ $\text{Mag} \approx 73\times$ (whole sample fitting the image)

Figure 11 Examples of overview images

Figure 14c Example of fracture surface imaging

2.5.3 Details of initiation site (selected samples):

- Same parameters as in 2.5.1
- Change: WD \approx 7 mm; z \approx 18 mm
- Imaging mode: depth mode
- Probe current I_p = 500 pA
- Image resolution: 2048 × 1536
- Both, SE and backscatter electron (BSE) detectors used simultaneously
- Mag < 4000×: All samples
 - One quick image with and without crosshair (SE only) at low mag, so that right and left edge of sample are still visible
 - 2 images (SE+BSE) at 200× (scan speed = 7, Line Avg. 4; at least 1.5 min / image)
 - 2 images (SE+BSE) at 500× (scan speed = 7, Line Avg. 4; at least 1.5 min / image)
 - 2 images (SE+BSE) at 1000× (scan speed = 8, Line Avg. 4; at least 2 min / image)
 - 2 images (SE+BSE) at 2000× (scan speed = 8, Line Avg. 4; at least 2 min / image)

Figure 15a (Left sample) Example of images of fracture initiation site

Figure 16b (Right sample) Example of images of fracture initiation site

2.5.4 Details of initiation site, high magnification imaging (selected samples):

- Same parameters as in 2.5.3
- Mag \geq 4000x:
 - Imaging mode: depth mode
 - $I_p = 200$ pA
 - One image at 5000 \times (scan speed = 8, Line Avg. 12, 8 min / image)
- Mag \geq 8000x:
 - Imaging mode: resolution mode o $I_p \leq 200$ pA
 - One image at 10000 \times (scan speed = 8, Line Avg. 16, 10.8 min / image)

In the present example, the initiation site consists of some large MnS particles surrounded by an area of intergranular fracture. A clear initiation location cannot be determined, so that high magnification images are not necessary. For other sample (e.g. with small carbide in initiation centre), high magnification images are important:

Figure 17 Example of high magnification images of fracture initiation site (from a different sample)

2.5.5 EDX characterisation (selected samples):

- 50 µm aperture
- Acceleration voltage = 12 kV
- WD ≈ 10 mm; z ≈ 15 mm
- Imaging mode: resolution mode
- Probe current $I_p = 1000$ pA
- Image resolution: 1024x768
- Measurement mode: spot mode, chosen positions on the image on and around the initiation site
- If a particle is found, enough spots should be chosen to mark the particle out
- First measurement on steel matrix, as reference
- Measurement time per spot: ≥ 2 min
- Files saved for each spot:
 - Image with position marker
 - Spectrum as .spx file
 - Spectrum as excel file
 - Spectrum image with elements
 - Spectrum image without elements

Figure 18a (Left sample) Example of images showing location at which spectrum acquired, plus spectra with and without peak identification.

Figure 19b (Right sample) Example of images showing location at which spectrum acquired, plus spectra with and without peak identification.

3 References

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